

Softmax Similarity Weighting for Bottom-up Building Stock Modelling: Application to Building Replacements in Zurich (2001–2019)

Jingxian YE*

ENAC, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Fribourg, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT. The building material stock plays a pivotal role in the circular economy by reducing reliance on virgin resources through material reuse and recovery. Realizing this potential requires accurate mapping of urban material flows, yet such efforts are often hindered by missing material-specific data in cadastral and GIS records. Among bottom-up estimation approaches, Similarity weighting (SW) is a novel method that infers unknown building properties from known samples via similarity-based averaging. While SW addresses the oversimplifications of conventional archetype models, it remains limited by subjective parameter selection, a coverage–accuracy trade-off, and reduced efficacy in high-dimensional contexts—all constraining its generalizability. To overcome these challenges, this study proposes Softmax Similarity Weighting (SoftmaxSW), a reformulation of classical SW method (inverse-distance-weighting) into a probabilistic similarity-based approach. This shift improves generalizability by enabling adaptation to diverse data conditions, enhancing numerical stability, and ensuring consistent performance across varying feature dimensions, while maintaining high coverage and accuracy. Additional branches integrate a radius scaling function to account for real-world interval-dependent shifts, such as temporal variations in material usage patterns. The method is applied to building replacements (BR) in Zurich City (2001–2019), estimating structural material use and embodied carbon emissions for 6,115 demolished and constructed buildings. Validation on 48 Swiss sample buildings shows 100% theoretical applicability and over 75% accuracy. SoftmaxSW matches the overall performance of Support Vector Machine and outperforms it in material-specific predictions. Results highlight slabs and walls, concrete, and multi-residential and office buildings as key areas for circularity within the BR context. Overall, SoftmaxSW provides a generalizable bottom-up framework for scalable interpolation of localized assessments, including material quantities and carbon emissions, and further extends to technological performance and other context-specific aspects relevant to urban-scale applications.

INTRODUCTION

Building stock modelling (BSM) is commonly classified into two approaches: top-down and bottom-up. Top-down models summarize entire stocks using macroeconomic statistics [1] but lack resolution to capture building-level characteristics. In contrast, bottom-up approaches are considered better suited to supporting the circular economy, as they enable detailed stock analysis and facilitate investigation of potential reuse of stockpiled materials as secondary resources [2]. Bottom-up approaches typically consist of two methods: building-by-building and archetype approaches. The former offers high resolution but demands rich, detailed data. Although advanced techniques such as remote sensing and computer vision have been developed to enhance data collection capabilities, these methods are primarily suited for existing buildings and exterior components, and are not applicable to demolished buildings or interior elements. Archetype approaches represent building cohorts through archetypes and extrapolate findings across the stock using up-scaling factors. However, cohort categorization often relies on expert judgment, and propagation through up-scaling assumes homogeneity in material composition,

*The corresponding author, independent scholar, formerly at EPFL: emilyyip1129@gmail.com.

intensity, and other characteristics within each category. Archetype-based approaches are therefore criticized for oversimplifying models [3], homogenizing datasets, and resulting in a loss of heterogeneity [4]. To address these issues, Fivet and team [5] introduced a novel bottom-up approach in 2024, using a *similarity-weighting* (SW) function to estimate unknown properties of stock buildings through weighted averages of similar samples, with weights linearly derived from feature-based differences (Figure 1, left). However, this method presents several limitations: (1) **Subjectivity**: Defining similar samples through similarity boundaries often requires manually setting threshold values, which introduces subjective assumptions. Moreover, a fixed and uniform boundary fails to capture real-world variations and nonlinear behaviors—for example, the evolving historical trajectories and time-dependent adoption patterns of different materials; (2) **Trade-off in coverage vs. accuracy**: A wider boundary allows broader comparisons but reduces accuracy, while a narrower one ensures stricter similarity but limits comparable samples and lowers validation coverage. This challenge is particularly acute in the building sector, where sample data is often limited and sparse; (3) **High-dimensional ineffectiveness**: Euclidean distance is more effective as a similarity measure in low-dimensional spaces (1–3D). In higher dimensions, the phenomenon of “distance concentration” can easily occur—relative differences among inter-point distances diminish, and the ratio between the nearest and farthest distances approaches 1—thereby weakening discriminative power and undermining similarity measures based on absolute distances between features.

Therefore, this study tackles these limitations by developing a generalizable bottom-up method designed to overcome subjectivity, improve validation coverage and accuracy, and maintain performance across diverse feature spaces. This method quantifies and maps the in-use stock, demand, and release of distinct building materials, along with their associated embodied carbon, to better inform circular strategies targeting material circularity. Central to the approach is a SW scheme incorporating the *Softmax* function, a widely used and effective similarity technique, providing a robust framework for detailed stock modeling. In addition, the method accounts for the nonlinear behavior of different materials, particularly their historically incremental phase-in and phase-out patterns. Finally, this study traces conceptual origins of SW and examines its applicability and limitations in the BSM context.

METHODS

Softmax Similarity Weighting for Generic Cases

The core principle of SW originates from the *inverse-distance-weighting* (IDW) interpolation method developed in the 1960s at Harvard’s Computer Graphics Laboratory [6]. It estimates the value at an unobserved geographical point as a weighted average of known points, where weights decay with distance following a power law, thereby assigning greater weight to closer points. This method has broad applications across environmental science (e.g., air quality), geology (e.g., mineral exploration), and economics (e.g., real estate pricing). Assuming this interpolation applies to BSM, the general formula is expressed as:

$$M(j) = \frac{\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j) M(i)}{\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j)}, \quad (1)$$

where $M(i)$ and $M(j)$ represent *interpolable properties* of sample i and stock building j , such as material quantities, emissions profiles, or technology-specific effects. An *interpolable property* refers to a characteristic determined by objective conditions, excluding behavior- or policy-dependent attributes like lifespan. The sample and stock sets are denoted by $\mathcal{I} = \{i\}$ and $\mathcal{J} = \{j\}$. Let $C(j)$ denote the subset of samples within \mathcal{I} that satisfy eligibility conditions (e.g., matching use category or industrial zone) for comparison with stock building j , over which the summation index i runs. The weight $w(i, j)$ quantifies similarity based on distance $D(i, j)$ in feature space. The denominator $\sum_{i \in C(j)} w(i, j)$ acts as a normalization factor, ensuring that the weights estimate $M(j)$ sum to 1. While the SW method proposed by Fivet *et al.* [5] uses a **linear decay weighting** scheme (Figure 1, left)—equivalent to IDW with a power parameter of

Figure 1. Diagram of weight assignments for stock building j : (left) a linear weighting in SW, derived from Fivet *et al.* [5]; (right) an exponential weighting in SoftmaxSW. In SW, only samples within the boundary contribute (active), while others are ignored (inactive). SoftmaxSW assigns weights to all samples (all active). 1—and manually defined elliptical boundaries that constrain the comparison scope, this study instead employs an **exponential decay function** to assign weights that decay smoothly with increasing feature distance (Figure 1, right), expressed as:

$$w(i, j) = e^{-\sigma D(i, j)}. \quad (2)$$

Combining Eqs. 1 and 2, the normalized weighting function follows a **Softmax** mapping, widely used in Large Language Models to convert distance-based measures into smooth, differentiable similarity weights [7]. This design offers several advantages: (1) **Adaptive behavior**: The exponential decay amplifies differences by assigning higher weights to nearby samples and rapidly downweighting distant ones, removing the need for predefined similarity boundaries and enhancing coverage and robustness. The hyperparameter σ controls sensitivity to distance; larger values produce sharper decay and more focused weights; (2) **Numerical stability**: Typical IDW can become unstable when distances between samples approach zero, as the weight expression diverges—a phenomenon known as “weight explosion”—which may lead to numerical errors such as undefined values (*NaN*) or overflow (*Inf*). In contrast, Softmax produces bounded and smooth weights, and further improves stability through the LogSumExp trick; (3) **High-dimensional robustness**: IDW is vulnerable to the “distance concentration” effect, where distances become indistinguishable and weights tend to equalize or become discontinuous. Softmax can amplify relative weight differences by introducing σ , making it robust for distinguishing samples in high dimensions. Critically, the transformation from IDW to Softmax reframes absolute distance-based interpolation as probabilistic similarity assignment, enabling a weighting scheme with greater generalizability: namely, adaptability, stability, and scalability.

The separation between stock and sample buildings are quantified by the Euclidean distance

$$D(i, j) = \sqrt{\sum_k (\Delta F_k(i, j) / \tilde{F}_k)^2}, \quad (k = 1, 2, \dots, n), \quad (3)$$

where F represents the features used for similarity comparison, indexed by k . Feature selection is context-dependent and should reflect the mechanisms or correlates of the interpolable property. It may include numerical attributes (e.g., year, size, coordinates) and categorical attributes (e.g., functionality, district), with categorical features converted into binary form via one-hot encoding. Each feature difference is normalized by a scaling factor \tilde{F}_k —set to 1 for binary features and based on distribution metrics (e.g., standard deviation) for numerical features—to remove unit effects and balance contributions. Categorical attributes are either used as prerequisites to filter samples i sharing the category of j in Eq. 1 to define the comparison set, or incorporated in one-hot encoded distance metrics, depending on the application. Hence, the method proposed is called **Softmax Similarity Weighting**, abbreviated as **SoftmaxSW**.

Extension with Dynamic Similarity Boundary for Interval-Dependent Behavior

The basic SW principle in IDW assumes a smoothly distributed dataset. However, real-world phenomena often exhibit **nonlinear behavior with interval-dependent shifts**, where behavior varies across conditions or ranges and may change abruptly at critical points. For instance,

material elasticity varies with stress levels, and biological growth rates shift with age. In buildings, material usage does not always follow a continuous trend, with discontinuities such as structural material per unit area surging beyond certain heights [8] or materials phasing in and out at key technological milestones. These patterns challenge the smooth distribution assumption underlying SW-based methods, necessitating alternatives. A *piecewise function* effectively captures variations in feature F_k across distinct intervals [9], fitting transitions driven by temporal dynamics or contextual shifts. To ensure similarity estimation respects this piecewise behavior, a **similarity boundary** is introduced to constrain comparisons within the same behavioral regime. This boundary corresponds to the piecewise structure: if interval thresholds remain stable, the boundary stays fixed; but when thresholds evolve, it must be dynamically adjusted—forming a **dynamic similarity boundary** that adapts to evolving piecewise regimes. For example, the adoption pattern of a specific material in stock buildings evolves over time, leading to dynamic adjustments of the corresponding similarity boundary. A narrow boundary indicates early or limited adoption phases, where the material appears in few cases and exhibits inconsistent features, requiring stricter similarity criteria for reliable comparison. Conversely, a wider boundary reflects broader adoption, where the material is used across varied contexts and features tend to stabilize and diversify, allowing greater variability tolerance while preserving meaningful similarity. Applying a uniform boundary across all measured indicators and materials risks overgeneralization, as observed in the SW application by [5].

To mathematically characterize and dynamically adjust the similarity boundary associated with a specific feature F within the SoftmaxSW framework, a *radius scaling function* $\gamma(\cdot)$ is introduced. This function defines a similarity boundary radius for feature F , dynamically scaled by the value of F in stock building j , denoted as $\gamma(F(j))$. Specifically, the distance function (Eq. 3) is modified, subject to the constraint:

$$(\Delta F(i, j)/\tilde{F})^2 \leq \gamma(F(j)). \quad (4)$$

A dynamic similarity boundary is needed only when interval-dependent shifts must be explicitly captured—for instance, when material types phase in or out over time due to technological evolution. In contrast, essential and time-invariant intrinsic properties like spatial size or total mass are well captured by SoftmaxSW for generic consideration without such boundaries.

APPLICATION AND VALIDATION

The SoftmaxSW method is applied to building replacements (BR) in Zurich City from 2001 to 2019 to estimate the inflow and outflow of structural materials and associated embodied greenhouse gas emissions (EGHGEs). The stock dataset comprises 3,359 demolished buildings dating from 1780 to 2018 and 2,756 newly constructed buildings between 2001 and 2019. The sample dataset, derived from [10], comprises 48 Swiss buildings: 32 residential (R) and 16 non-residential (NR). Detailed investigation data cover structural components (slabs, beams, walls, posts, roofing frameworks, and covers), excluding foundations, stairs, and balconies. Construction materials—reinforced concrete, metals, timber, and masonry—are assessed in terms of volume, mass, and EGHGE (phases A1–A3 per EN-15978) using KBOB.

Prerequisite condition. The attribute of functionality is selected as the prerequisite in Eq. 1.

Figure 2. SoftmaxSW-based bottom-up workflow transfers observed properties from limited samples to the broader stock; the red box marks the interpolated target.

This work adopts two coarse-grained groups, residential (R) and non-residential (NR), as the basis for similarity matching, restricting comparisons to buildings within the same category.

Similarity comparison. Comparison features, including built year, footprint, and building height, are chosen for their availability and relevance to the estimated properties.

Parameter selection. The parameter σ in weighting function is empirically set to 0.8, achieving a local minimum mean absolute percentage error and producing a slower decay rate compared to the standard exponential setting of 1. The normalization factors \bar{F} for construction year, footprint, and height are determined based on their standard deviations across the datasets.

Material-specific scaling functions. Compared to the SW application in [5], this study refines material-specific estimation in SoftmaxSW by introducing distinct radius scaling functions γ for three materials, capturing their respective historical evolutions and adoption rates. Concrete, metal, and timber and masonry correspond to γ_c , γ_m , and γ_{ts} , respectively.

Cross validation. All methods are validated by cross-predicting each sample building’s quantity from the remaining ones, with performance evaluated using mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and model coverage (Table 1). For SW and SoftmaxSW, leave-one-out cross-validation is applied. SoftmaxSW achieves full coverage, while SW reaches 87.5%. SoftmaxSW also provides more accurate estimates, with overall accuracy between 75–80%. Further compared with Support Vector Machine (SVM), a classic machine learning effective for training on small to medium datasets. MATLAB’s `fitrsvm` with automatic hyperparameter tuning is called, which defaults to 5-fold cross-validation. Results show SoftmaxSW matches or outperforms SVM. As estimation granularity increases for breakdown materials, both methods see rising error rates, with SoftmaxSW generally performing better. A higher presence of zero values in the sample set correlates with increased error rates, particularly for metals, where the high errors observed in SoftmaxSW are attributed to exceptionally high quantity estimates in several samples where metals were present, leading to a steep rise in overall error rate. Since the total quantity of metals is small, the impact on the total estimation error remains limited.

Correlation between measures. The high cosine similarity and Pearson correlation coefficient (PCC) between the estimated measures (volume, mass, and EGHGE) confirm strong correlations, further validating SoftmaxSW. Additionally, PCC values are higher for new construction than for demolition, indicating better model performance for new construction.

Table 1. Model performance on the sample dataset using cross-validation across SW, SoftmaxSW, and SVM.

Estimated measures	Number of 0 value in sample library	SW [5]		SoftmaxSW		SVM	
		Coverage \uparrow	MAPE \downarrow	Coverage \uparrow	MAPE \downarrow	Coverage \uparrow	MAPE \downarrow
EGHGE	0	87.5%	26.74%	100%	20.58 %	100%	20.08%
Volume	0	87.5%	31.21%	100%	25.75 %	100%	37.26%
Mass	0	87.5%	33.98%	100%	26.71 %	100%	26.42%
concrete mass	3	—	—	100%	44.96% ($+\gamma_c$)	100%	89.19%
metal mass	36	—	—	100%	453.71% ($+\gamma_m$)	100%	399.32%
timber mass	31	—	—	100%	46.64% ($+\gamma_{ts}$)	100%	132.94%
masonry mass	26	—	—	100%	63.90% ($+\gamma_{ts}$)	100%	41.76%

RESULTS

This study uses the SoftmaxSW method to estimate material quantities and embodied carbon emissions for BR projects in Zurich (2001–2019), achieving 90% coverage; the remaining 10% of building entries lacked complete data. The results show that while new constructions had 2.44 times the total volume of demolished buildings, their structural volume, mass, and EGHGEs (A1–A3) were 2.26, 2.53, and 2.24 times higher, respectively. Structural EGHGEs per unit (in $\text{kgCO}_2\text{eq/m}^2$) for residential buildings (211 for demolished, 218 for new) were slightly above the 25th percentile structural GWP (around 200, A1–A3) in the deQo database [11], likely due to excluding foundations and staircases. A more detailed breakdown reveals three key patterns. First, the distribution of EGHGEs across structural components is similar between demolition and new construction in BR, with slabs and walls dominating—accounting for over 85% and 92% of total EGHGE, respectively. Except for beams, the absolute EGHGE of each

component is higher in new construction. Second, concrete is the primary structural material, increasing from 84.5% in demolitions to 99.5% in new constructions. Third, demolished concrete structures mainly originate from multi-residential, office, and industrial buildings, whereas new construction is dominated by multi-residential and office buildings, accounting for 75.7% and 15.2% of total structural concrete use, respectively. These findings highlight slabs and walls, concrete, and multi-residential and office buildings as key focus areas for investigating circularity in structural components, materials, and building types within the BR context.

DISCUSSION FOR METHODOLOGY

SoftmaxSW provides a generalizable bottom-up approach, demonstrating robustness to data variability, reliable numerical behavior, and consistent performance across low- and high-dimensional feature spaces. These qualities enable its effective extension to diverse urban contexts and datasets. SoftmaxSW proved effective even with limited samples, highlighting its suitability for BSM, where data are often limited and sparse due to manual collection. Its accuracy improves with sample size. SW-based methods rely on the assumption of smoothly varying data, making them suitable for domains governed by stable industry trends or objectively defined technologies, such as structural and envelope assemblies. In contrast, user-driven assemblies such as finishes exhibit higher variability and greater uncertainty in SW assignment. Although the radius scaling function captures real-world interval-dependent behavior, it remains a conceptual abstraction and warrants further investigation. In conclusion, SoftmaxSW enables accurate bottom-up mapping of material flows and emissions, supporting circular resource planning in construction. It supports scalable interpolation of localized assessments across physical, technological, and other domains relevant to urban-scale applications.

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